

ABSTRACTS of the

**7th Meeting of the European Section
and
8th Meeting of the North American Section
of the
International Academy of Cardiovascular
Sciences (IACS)**

Banja Luka, 20-23 September 2021

Organised by:

International Academy of Cardiovascular Sciences (IACS) – European and North American Sections

University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Serbian Association of Arteriosclerosis, Trombosis and Vascular Biology Research, Belgrade, Serbia

Association for Atherosclerosis and Cardiovascular Research, Banja Luka,
the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Meeting Committees

Presidency

RANKO ŠKRBIĆ, Chair

MILOŠ P STOJILJKOVIĆ, Co-Chair

International Organising & Programme Committee

ROBERTO BOLLI, President, IACS (Louisville, KY, USA)

NARANJAN S DHALLA, Founder and CEO, IACS (Winnipeg, MB, Canada)

GARY LOPASCHUK, President, North American Section, IACS (Edmonton, AB, Canada)

BOHUSLAV OŠTÁDAL, Past president, IACS (Prague, Czech Republic)

GRANT N PIERCE, President-Elect, IACS (Winnipeg, MB, Canada)

ANDRAS VARRO, President, European Section, IACS (Szeged, Hungary)

International Programme Committee

Devendra K Agrawal, Pomona, CA, USA

Istvan Baczkó, Szeged, Hungary

Monika Barteková, Bratislava, Slovakia

Maciej Banach, Łódź, Poland

Jerzy Beltowski, Lubin, Poland

Roberto Bolli, Louisville, KY, USA

Tonino Bombardini, Pisa, Italy

Harpal S Buttar, Ottawa, ON, Canada

Michael Czubryt, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Buddhadeb Dawn, Las Vegas, NV, USA

Naranjan S Dhalla, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Sanjiv Dhingra, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Mirza Dilić, Sarajevo, Bosnia & Herzegovina

Dragan M Djuric, Belgrade, Serbia

Igor Efimov, Washington, DC, USA

Brent M Egan, Greenville, SC, USA

Peter Ferdinandy, Budapest, Hungary

Ferenc Gallyas, Pécs, Hungary

Vladimir L Jakovljevic, Kragujevac, Serbia

Ana Jerončić, Split, Croatia

Lorrie A Kirshenbaum, Winnipeg, MB, CA

Rakesh C. Kukreja, Richmond, VA, USA

Vincenzo Lionetti, Pisa, Italy

Gary Lopaschuk, Edmonton, AB, Canada

Martin Morad, Charleston, SC, USA

Danina Muntean, Timisoara, Romania

Bohuslav Oštádal, Prague, Czech Republic

Petr Oštádal, Prague, Czech Republic

Miodrag Ć Ostojić, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoltan Papp, Debrecen, Hungary

Grant N Pierce, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Tanya Ravingerova, Bratislava, Slovakia

Alan P Robertson, Ames, IA, USA

Dineder Singla, Orlando, FL, USA

Jan Slezak, Bratislava, Slovakia

Šekib Sokolović, Sarajevo, Bos.-Herzegovina

Paramjit Tappia, Winnipeg, MB, Canada

Srinivas Tipparaju, Tampa, FL, USA

Gregor Tratar, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Belma Turan, Ankara, Turkey

Suresh C Tyagi, Louisville, KY, USA

Andras Varro, Szeged, Hungary

Nathan D Wong, Irvine, CA, USA

Local Programme and CME Planning Committee

Branko Beleslin, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragan M Djuric, Belgrade, Serbia

Ana Đorđević-Dikić, Belgrade, Serbia

Ljiljana C Gojković-Bukarica, Belgrade, SRB

Vladimir L Jakovljevic, Kragujevac, Serbia

Nina Japundžić-Žigon, Belgrade, Serbia

Katarina S Lalić, Belgrade, Serbia

Nebojša M Lalić, Belgrade, Serbia

Goran Lončar, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragana Lončar-Stojiljković, Belgrade, Serbia

Amela Matavulj, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Momir M Mikov, Novi Sad, Serbia

Milan Milojević, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoran Miloradović, Belgrade, Serbia

Milan A Nedeljković, Belgrade, Serbia

Lana Nežić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miodrag Ć Ostojić, Belgrade, Serbia

Petar Otašević, Belgrade, Serbia

Miodrag Perić, Belgrade, Serbia

Nenad Ponorac, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miroslav Radenković, Belgrade, Serbia

Tatjana Simić, Belgrade, Serbia

Tanja Šobot, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Svjetlana Stoisavljević-Šatara, BL, RS, BA

Nataša Stojaković, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Miloš P Stojiljković, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Ranko Škrbić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Nebojša M Tasić, Belgrade, Serbia

Zoran Todorović, Belgrade, Serbia

Duško Vulić, Banja Luka, RS, BA

Local Organising Committee

Đorđe Đukanović, Banja Luka

Ana Golić, Banja Luka

Milkica Grabež

Žana M Maksimović, Banja Luka

Nataša Miljuš, Banja Luka

Sonja Trbojević, Banja Luka

Cardioprotective Potential of Semisynthetic Bile Acids – Rational Drug Design

Slavica Lazarević,¹ Maja Đanić,¹ Nebojša Pavlović,² Saša Vukmirović,¹ Bojan Stanimirov,³ Momir Mikov¹

Abstract

Recently, bile acids (BA) and their derivatives have been frequently mentioned as signaling molecules regulating metabolic homeostasis through farnesoid X receptor (FXR) and Takeda G-protein receptor-5 (TGR5 receptor) which became attractive targets for treating dyslipidemia and cardiovascular disease. Consequently, there is a high need for the design and synthesis of potent, selective and pharmacokinetically improved ligands for these clinically useful receptors. The aim of this review is to summarize main advances regarding the cardioprotective mechanisms of semisynthetic BA derivatives with focus on the importance of key chemical modifications.

One of the semisynthetic BA derivatives, INT-777, designed as a potent TGR5 modulator has been shown to have therapeutic potential in atherosclerosis. A study conducted by Pols et al.¹ proposed that its inhibition of cytokines is associated with TGR5 activation of the cAMP-NF-κB signaling pathway and decrease of oxidized LDL uptake in macrophages. However, the reduction could be a consequence of the lower expression level of scavenger receptor A (SR-A) and cluster of differentiation 36 (CD36), hence further investigation should be undertaken. The *in vivo* study investigating INT-767,² first-identified compound that potently and selectively activates both BA receptors, demonstrated that the lipid-lowering effect is a consequence of FXR-mediated inhibition of CYP8B1 and CYP7A1 expression, enzymes involved in BAs synthesis, and induction of SR-BI and ATP-binding cassette sub-family B member 4 (ABCB4), hepatic genes involved in cholesterol efflux to feces. On the other hand, anti-inflammatory effects of this potential drug candidate, which play a crucial role in atherosclerotic plaque prevention, are based exclusively on TGR5 activation. According to these observations, simultaneous activation of FXR and TGR5 could provide the maximum beneficial effect in cardiovascular disorders. Despite this promising data, more studies are needed to elucidate the role of the dual FXR/TGR5 agonist in this aspect.

Small alterations in BA chemical structure could provide targeted activation of various signaling cascades mediated by nuclear receptors, thus leading to desired therapeutic effects. In addition, a beneficial effect of the BA scaffold manipulations is the design of derivatives with diminished cytotoxic properties.

Key words: Bile acid derivatives; FXR; TGR5; Cardiovascular; Atherosclerosis.

Reference: 1. Pols TW, Nomura M, Harach T, Sasso GL, Oosterveer MH, Thomas C, et al. TGR5 activation inhibits atherosclerosis by reducing macrophage inflammation and lipid loading. *Cell Metab* 2011;14(6):747-57. 2. Miyazaki-Anzai S, Masuda M, Levi M, Keenan AL, Miyazaki M. Dual activation of the bile acid nuclear receptor FXR and G-protein-coupled receptor TGR5 protects mice against atherosclerosis. *PLoS One* 2014 Sep 19;9(9):e108270. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0108270.

- (1) Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.
- (2) Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.
- (3) Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia.

Correspondence:
SLAVICA LAZAREVIĆ
E: slavica_vukoje@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT INFO

Abstract ID: 126
Submitted: 9 September 2021